

RULES OF DISPUTES IN THE FIELD OF JURISPRUDENCE

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Abstract This article talks about the debate and its types, the rules to be followed in conducting the debate, and the set of etiquette to be followed in front of the audience.

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Nowadays, many problems can only be solved through open and transparent exchange of ideas, public dialogues and civil agreements. To know how to correctly and effectively discuss life's important issues, to be able to prove one's point of view and to be convinced of it, to be able to stand firm in it and to deny the opinions of the opposite side, that is, to have the skill to enter into a discussion Being is one of the qualities that every educated person should have. The concept of "debating skills" includes knowing the topic of the debate, understanding the nature of the public debate and its types, following the basic requirements of the debate culture, being able to prove the position advanced and reject the opinions of the opposing side, using debate methods, being able to oppose the arguments of the opposing side. includes having qualities such as

There are different types of disputes. In scientific and methodical literature, they try to systematize them. Various signs are taken as a basis, but the final classification of disputes has not yet been created. The main factors affecting the nature of the dispute and its characteristics include: the purpose of the dispute, the number of participants, the form of conducting the dispute. Based on these factors, we will analyze what types of disputes can be distinguished.

It is known that people do not have a single goal when entering into an argument, they are influenced by various factors. Arguments by purpose are divided

into the following types: an argument for the truth, an argument to convince someone, an argument to win, an argument for an argument.

Debate serves as a means to search for the truth, to check certain thoughts, ideas, and to justify them. In order to find the right solution, polemicists compare different views on a particular problem. They defend an idea against various counter-arguments in order to find out what objections there may be to this idea, or, conversely, oppose the ideas of the opposing side and determine what evidence is available in its favor. In such a debate, evidence and evidence are carefully selected and analyzed. The opinions and ideas of the opposite parties are comparatively evaluated, that is, in essence, the truth is sought together. Of course, such a debate can be between people who know this problem and are interested in its solution. Russian philosopher, logician, Professor Sergei Povarnin, who developed the theory of debate at the beginning of the 20th century: "Besides the undoubted usefulness of the argument for the truth, it has its own beauty, which gives real pleasure and satisfaction to the participants of the debate. Also, it truly serves as "Food for the Mind". As a result of such a mental struggle, a person feels more uplifted and better. And even if you have to retreat, give in, give up the idea that you are defending, but the unpleasant feeling of defeat will go into the background."

Arguments can be conducted not to seek the truth, but also to convince the other party. There are two important cases. The debater convinces the other side of what he firmly believes. Secondly, sometimes he has to convince the other party about his duty or some situation. But he himself does not believe in its truth or does not believe in the falsity of the opposite party's opinion. In this case, the goal of the debate is not to learn or to convince, but to win. In this case, polemicists achieve victory with the help of various motives. Some of them are firm in their point of view. They protect public interests.

Some people need victory just to show themselves. Therefore, it is very important for them to succeed in the debate, to be highly appreciated by others, to

be recognized for their intellectual abilities, and to have a reputation. Others just like to win. They want victory to be more effective. They are not ashamed of the methods and means they choose to win.

Often there is a dispute for the sake of the dispute. This is a kind of argument, it's like saying art for art's sake. Such debaters do not care what to argue about, who to argue about, and why. They just like to attract attention with their eloquence, to prove that white is black or black is white. If you deny some idea, they will certainly start to defend it. Such polemicists can often be found among young people.

Such categorization of the types of disputes according to their purpose has a conditional character in a certain sense. In life, they are not always clearly separated. Having won the argument, the polemicist tries to convince the other party that his opinion is correct. And in order to convince the other side of something, searching for the truth and clarifying the proposed opinion will help to make more correct decisions.

Debates can take place with or without an audience. The presence of an audience affects debaters even if they do not contribute to the debate. The victory achieved in front of the audience gives more satisfaction. Defeat is more painful and unpleasant. Therefore, the participants taking part in the debate next to the audience take into account those around them, their reactions. They carefully select the necessary evidence. They are firm in their opinions and sometimes get overheated.

Public debates are also common. The debate is conducted not to search for the truth, to convince each other, but to attract attention to the problem, to make a certain impression on the audience, to have an appropriate influence. The process is also affected by the form of conducting the battle of ideas. Disputes can be oral or written. The oral form is based on the direct communication of certain individuals with each other. Written form is based on mediated communication. Oral arguments are usually limited in time and closed in space. They are conducted at trainings, conferences, meetings, various events, etc. The written form is more continuous in

time than the oral form. Because communication between disputing parties will be mediated. External and psychological aspects play an important role in oral arguments, especially if it is conducted in front of an audience. Demonstrating self-confidence, quick response, lively thinking and a sharp mind approach are of great importance here. A timid and shy person usually loses a fight against a confident opponent. Therefore, a written argument is more useful than an oral one to determine the truth. However, it also has its drawbacks. It sometimes goes on for a long time and even lasts for several years. Readers and participants of the debate will forget specific cases and conclusions. They will not be able to restore them in memory. Sometimes the debate is carried out on the pages of different publications, which makes it difficult to follow.

Disputes will be structured and unstructured. Organized debates are planned, prepared and conducted under the supervision of experts. Polemicists will have the opportunity to familiarize themselves with the topic of the debate in advance, determine their position, find the necessary evidence, and think of answers to the objections that the opposing side may raise.

But the dispute can happen unexpectedly. Such situations are often observed in daily communication during the educational process, meetings, meetings. Unorganized, impromptu debates usually have low results. In such debates, the participants' statements are not sufficiently substantiated and sometimes lead to unexpected conclusions, and in such debates, opinions are expressed that are not as mature as they should be.

The success of the debate depends on its structure, effectiveness in solving problems, and to a certain extent the composition of the polemicists. It is important for them to have the level of culture, knowledge, intelligence, life experience, skills and knowledge of debating, and to know the rules of public debate.

References:

1. Рахмонова, Д. М. МУЛОҚОТНИНГ ЎЗИГА ХОСЛИКЛАРИ: ПРОФИЛАКТИКА ИНСПЕКТОРЛАРИНИНГ ДЕВИАНТ ХУЛҚ-АТВОРЛИ ФУҚАРОЛАР БИЛАН ИШЛАШ МУАММОЛАРИ. *INVOLTA*.
2. Yusupov, A., & Mirzakarimovna, R. D. (2022). INSON HUQUQ VA ERKINLIKLARINI TA'MINLASHDA KONSTITUTSIYANING O'RNI. *INNOVATIVE DEVELOPMENT IN THE GLOBAL SCIENCE*, 1(3), 112-115.
3. Mirzakarimovna, R. D. (2022). KONSTITUTSIYAVIY ISLOHOTLAR–HUQUQIY TARAQQIYOT GAROVI. *INNOVATIVE DEVELOPMENT IN THE GLOBAL SCIENCE*, 1(3), 116-119.
4. Mirzakarimovna, R. D., & Mirsharof o'g'li, A. M. (2022). JAMIYATDA AYOLLAR: GENDER TENGLIGI VA FEMINIZM MOHIYATI TAHLILI. *Gospodarka i Innowacje.*, 25, 84-86.